

Electrometric Studies on Clay-Fulvic Acid Interactions

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Manuscript received 29 July 1976, accepted 10 November 1976

The interactions between H-clays (original and oxide free) and fulvic acid fraction (F.A.) of soil humus were studied by electrometric titrations.

Conductometric studies show the formation of four different types of complexes with original clay and three different types with clay (oxide free) fractions. Potentiometric studies confirm these.

Besides reacting with metal ions, humic (H.A.) and fulvic (F.A.) acid fractions of soil organic matter are capable of interacting with clays to form complexes. Such interactions are of importance in the formation of stable aggregates. Mechanisms governing such reactions have been reviewed by Mortland¹ and Greenland².

In the present study some attempts have been made to provide information on the nature of interactions between clay-F.A., employing electrometric studies.

Experimental

Organic matter was extracted and fractionated from Bigra pond sediment, Dist. Burdwan, W.B. (0-15 cm depth), by the procedure adopted by Banerjee and Mukherjee³. As F.A. in solution gets

the aqueous suspension of Ba-fulvate through a column of Amberlite IR-120 in H-form. The F.A. thus obtained was repeatedly resin treated to reduce its inorganic constituents to the minimum.

After removal of organic matter from the sediment, it was treated with H₂O₂ to remove the residual organic matter. The excess H₂O₂ was removed by warming it to 80°-90° in water bath. The clay-fractions (<2μ) were collected from this by the usual process of dispersion and sedimentation. The clay isolated was treated with dil. HCl to convert it into H-clay which was then purified by dialysis. Finally these dialysed H-clay materials were shaken with a cation exchange resin (Amberlite IR-120 in the H-form) to get the H-clay. For preparation of oxide-free clay, the procedure as adopted by Mehra and Jackson⁴ was followed.

Fig.—1 (a)

slowly polymerised on standing, it was converted into its Ba-salt by treating it with BaCl₂ at pH 7-8. The precipitate was dialysed and finally electro-dialysed. F.A. was prepared fresh before use by passing

Fig.—1 (b)

Conductometric titration :

In a number of stoppered 10 ml volumetric flasks, fixed amount of clay and increasing amount

of F.A. solutions were added. The contents of these flasks were shaken for 12 hr and allowed to equilibrate for 7-8 days. The total volume was made upto 10 ml in each case. After equilibrium, conductances of these solutions were measured by Leeds-Northrup Conductivity Bridge at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$. Conductometric titrations of F.A.-fractions and F.A.-clay combinations with NaOH were also carried out.

Fig-1 (c)

Potentiometric titrations

Compositions of the complexes were determined from the inflexion points of the conductometric titration curves as shown in Fig. 1(a). From this knowledge, different complex species were prepared by mixing clay and F.A. in the different mole ratios. These were titrated with NaOH solution in Cambridge pH-meter at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$.

The conductometric and potentiometric titration curve of H-clay-F.A., H-clay (oxide free) F.A. and their complexes are shown in Figures 1(b,c,d and e).

Results and Discussions

The average molecular weight of the electro-dialysed F.A. and the clay were found by electrometric method⁵, to be 1330 and 30,000 respectively. The present discussions are based on such results.

Instantaneous conductometric titrations (curves not shown) of F. A. with H-clay are of continuous nature showing no complex formation. But discontinuous titration (after allowing to equilibrate) shows four inflexion points for original clay-F.A. and three for clay (oxide free)-F.A. titrations, indicating complex formation at these points, Fig.1(a). The molar compositions corresponding to the original clay-F.A. are 1 : 12, 1 : 24 and 1 : 36 and oxide free clay-F.A. are 1 : 42, 1 : 52 and 1 : 60 respectively.

The conductometric titration curves of original

clay, clay (oxide free) and their complexes with F.A. as shown in Figures 1(b and c) are quite distinctive in character. This indicates that hydrous oxides of iron, aluminium etc. are the most important materials involved in interactions between clays and organic compounds in soil. From the sharp increasing trend of conductance values of the clay-F.A. complexes with NaOH solution, it may be inferred that there is a possibility of formation of 'water bridge'-like compounds¹ linking polymeric F.A.-molecules to the exchangeable metal-cations of the clay surface as

the metal cation and -COOH is one of the functional groups of F.A. On interaction with NaOH, Na⁺ exchanges for polyvalent ions such as Ca⁺², Mg⁺², Fe⁺³, etc. present on the clay surface. A fresh clay sol. F.A. product does not show any sharp change in conductance measurements but the product on ageing shows this change. Clay sol on ageing actually changes to H-Al-clay system^{6,7}.

Fig-1 (d)

Potentiometric titration curve of F.A. and clay-F.A. complexes against standard NaOH are shown in Figs. 1(d and e). During the titrations of original clay with NaOH, the change of pH is initially slow, indicating a weak acidity. But after that, the nature of the curve begins to flatten. This may be due to accumulation of osmotically active Na⁺ ions in the mobile double layer of the clay surface, replacing the surface H⁺ ions of the clay.

In order to get an idea about the mechanism of clay-F.A. interactions, number of protons released from organic matter by addition of clay are assessed and shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—Number of protons released from F.A./mole of clay added.

pH	H-clay:F.A. complexes in mole ratio			
	1 : 12	1 : 16	1 : 24	1 : 36
4.5	—	—	0.08	0.07
5	0.05	—	1.2	1.4
5.5	0.07	—	1.3	2.6
6	0.09	4.1	1.6	3.7
6.5	1.2	4.5	2.7	6.0
7	1.9	5.1	4.1	—
7.5	3.0	—	5.6	—
8	3.7	—	—	—
8.5	4.9	—	—	—

From the data given in Table 1, it is evident that number of protons released from the organic matter increases with pH in all the four different clay-F.A. systems.

Fig.—1 (e)

It is evident that higher the concentration of organic matter, greater is the number of protons released and maximum number of protons released is approximately 6 in the case of complex having the molar composition of clay : F.A.=1 : 36.

From the data it may be inferred that the clay-F.A. complexes are more or less stable upto a certain pH, and above (cf. table 1) which they begin to break up, resulting in release of larger number of protons^a.

In the oxide free clay-F.A. interactions, number of protons released is much less than unity (not shown in Table) in most of the cases. This indicates that F.A. molecules have penetrated into the coordination shell of the surface hydroxyl layer of the clay in such a way that it is not sensitive to pH change. This corroborates the views of Edward and Bremner⁹.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (T.K.M.) is grateful to C.S. I.R., New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship.

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